

Quantum Resolution Entropy? Part II

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In this note, we try to consider entropy associated with a free particle. Classically, one might expect that such a particle has no entropy, but according to (1), a free classical particle has a minimum entropy of $-k \ln(2)$ because it is either being measured or not and these represent two possible different microstates with equal weight.

We go on to suggest that quantum mechanics encodes a specific piece of information of a free particle, namely momentum (linked to kinetic energy) in an entropic manner, namely the quantum resolution entropy of Part I. Interestingly, another piece of information, velocity, is not encoded in the same way, the difference perhaps being that p is linked to impulse hits. We suggest that the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ represents the entropy of a self-measure which establishes physically that one has momentum p in space. If a free particle interacts with a Bohm-Aharonov type of potential then ultimately E and p return to original values, but a phase shift is added to the wavefunction, ie. $\exp(ipx + \delta)$. This again, represents a measurement, we argue, which manifests itself again through resolution entropy, because such a particle will interfere with another which did interact with a Bohm Aharaonov potential. Finally, we argue that the ground state energy is also due to the self measurement property of a quantum particle. A particle in a potential measures itself to be bound and so a minimum momentum/energy is required for this. One does not have the classical picture which requires an external measurement to establish that the particle is bound. This is also automatically associated with resolution entropy.

Minimum Particle Entropy?

In (1) an interesting statement is made, namely:

“In particular, the basic property of observability implies that every physical system can have at least two states: it is being observed or it is not.”

This statement is used as evidence that a free particle, for example, has a minimum entropy of:

$$S_{\text{minimum}} = -k \ln(2) \quad ((1)).$$

We try to investigate this situation in a little more detail by first considering a coin toss. At first, a coin sits heads up and there is full information. Then, an interaction occurs, i.e. the toss, and one no longer knows the state of the coin. It is either heads up or something else. In this case, there is only one other alternative, tails. As a result, one has two possible microstates with equal probability weights and a Shannon's entropy calculation yields:

$$S = -k \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) = k \ln(2) \quad ((2))$$

We try to apply this argument to a free particle with momentum p . As it moves freely, it is in a known state p , but if it enters a region where interactions occur (the coin toss region), it may retain its p value or obtain a different one. As a result, there is a minimum of two states in the picture, p or not p . If one has no information about whether p changes or not, one might assign a probability weight of .5 and so obtain a minimum entropy of ::

$$k \ln(2) \quad ((3))$$

We try to interpret the statement of (1) in this manner. In this case, it is the uncertainty of the particle retaining its original value during an interaction which leads to the idea of entropy, but this is the same notion which applies to a coin toss. The case of a die toss is very similar, but one has information about the possible interaction results, whereas for the particle one assumes p or not p with equal probabilities.

In other words, the notion of entropy here, and in the coin toss situation, seems to be linked with interactions. We try to extend this idea to a quantum free particle, considering interactions and the idea of measurement which in itself involves interactions.

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle is associated with a wavefunction $\exp(ipx) / \sqrt{L}$ where L is length. This wavefunction does not contain all information about the particle, because speed is excluded. In other words, two particles with the same p , but different speeds and rest masses, have the same wavefunction. Thus, a wavefunction is not complete information, but rather contains specific probabilistic type information about an interaction variable p which is proportional to an impulse hit.

We try to compare the situation to a coin toss. An interaction (toss) occurs and there may be two outcomes, heads or tails, which require a separate external measurement which is considered not to disturb the coin. In the case of a quantum free particle, we assume no external nondisturbing measurement, but suggest an internal probabilistic measurement is implied by $\exp(ipx)$. This establishes the value p , but also describes how it interacts probabilistically in a spatial sense. In other words, the self-measurement represented by $\exp(ipx)$ also inherently represents resolution entropy (from Part I). This governs how the particle interacts with say a two-slit system to give rise to a spatial pattern which has spatial entropy which may be measured using Shannon's entropy with the probability:

$P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \exp(i p_1 \cdot r) + \exp(i p_2 \cdot r)$ ((2)) where p_1 and p_2 have the same magnitude and represent rays from each slit moving to the same point on a screen far away.

Bohm Aharonov Interaction

To see a second example in which the free particle wavefunction acts as an information source which is then linked to resolution entropy, one may consider an interaction with a Bohm

Aharonov type of potential Such a potential does not change the magnitude or direction of p , but leads to a phase shift. One might think of the interaction as delaying the particle in time for a short δt . The spatial wavefunction becomes:

$\exp(ipx + i\delta)$ where δ is the phase shift ((3))

As a result, the wavefunction appears to represent a self-measurement of something that occurred, but this is encoded in a probabilistic manner, i.e. linked to spatial entropy in the sense that ((3)) interferes with $\exp(ipx)$ for a particle which did not encounter the Bohm Aharonov potential. This gives rise to a spatial interference pattern which again represents spatial entropy.

Thus, we suggest that a quantum wavefunction is linked with a physical resolution type of probability associated with self-measurement. This is associated with what we called resolution entropy in Part I.

Ground State

A feature of quantum mechanical single particle bound states is that they have a minimum ground state energy which is greater than the classical value of zero. We suggest again that this is due to the self-measurement feature of the wavefunction. The quantum system must measure itself as being in a bound state. One cannot rely on the external nondisturbing measurements of classical physics. As a result, the wavefunction must have $\exp(ipx)$ components or motion and hence resolution entropy. As a result, there is a minimum ground state energy, but also a minimum resolution entropy as well. In other words, the idea of a wavefunction is not separable from a self-measurement which in turn is not separable from resolution entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the entropy of a coin is due to its interaction (i.e. a toss) which may lead to heads or tails with equal probabilistic weight. We suggest that a statement made in (1) about a particle having a minimum entropy of $-k \ln(2)$ follows from this same idea. The particle originally has a known p (like a heads up coin), but if it moves into an interaction region, one no longer knows whether it retains p or changes. If one assumes equal probabilistic weights, one obtains $k \ln(2)$ as a minimum entropy.. Thus, entropy is associated with interactions.

We suggest that a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ encodes self-measurement information and at the same time represents entropy. The higher p , the more order one has. The wavefunction does not represent all information as speed is not contained, but it contains probabilistic information about a piece of information relevant to interactions, namely momentum. This is encoded probabilistically in space and so one may have interference patterns (spatial entropy) due to interactions with two slits etc. Another example of the wavefunction acting as a self-measurement is the interaction with a Bohm Aharonov potential which only adds a phase $\exp(ipx + i\delta)$. This records a measurement, but at the same reveals itself experimentally through an interference with an $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. through spatial resolution

entropy. Finally, a third example of the self-measurement and associated resolution entropy is that of a quantum ground state. The system must measure itself as being bound and this leads to at least some $\exp(ipx)$ pieces, i.e. some energy and resolution entropy.. In other words, a quantum system must undergo self-measurement and this is associated with resolution entropy. One cannot classically make measurements which do not affect the system and so have information at no entropy cost. $\exp(ipx)$ encodes information, but at the cost of resolution entropy which has physical consequences.

References

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